

Structured metadata for reproducible data quality assessments

A standards-aware cross-disciplinary approach for modern research data management

Elisa Kasbohm*¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3767-7145>,
Stephan Struckmann¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5266-9396>

¹ Institute for Community Medicine, University Medicine Greifswald, Germany

*Correspondence: Elisa Kasbohm, elisa.kasbohm@uni-greifswald.de

Abstract

Ensuring data quality is a fundamental challenge for research data infrastructures, as flawed data may compromise results, waste resources, and ultimately undermine trust. While basic checks, such as detecting out-of-range values or missing data, are commonly employed [1], assessing the fitness of data for complex analyses requires more comprehensive strategies. This includes identifying internal inconsistencies across variables, detecting multivariate outliers, and evaluating potential biases introduced by procedural variables such as measurement devices or examiners [2].

Yet, such advanced assessments are rarely performed in a reproducible or transparent manner. The R package `dataquieR`, developed within the NFDI4Health initiative, DFG- and BMBF-funded projects, and the EU-funded `euCanSHare` project, addresses this gap by using structured metadata to configure data quality checks through spreadsheets [3], [4]. These metadata files capture expectations and context, such as variable roles, value constraints, or relevant thresholds, which serve as input for the automated generation of detailed quality reports. The process of annotating data quality metadata in specifically structured files that can be made publicly accessible serves to make expectations and requirements for the data transparent and reusable. Using these metadata as main input for automated data quality reports renders individual results as well as complete data quality assessments reproducible.

In this way, comprehensive data quality reports can be generated with `dataquieR` by a single function call, enabling domain experts with and without programming skills to implement reproducible workflows efficiently. Furthermore, the tool provides functionalities to create custom data quality reports, and can be incorporated into existing data management pipelines.

`dataquieR` has already been linked to external standards or tools such as CDISC's ODM and REDCap, with further extensions (e.g., HL7 FHIR) under way. Its metadata-driven logic and infrastructure orientation make it applicable across disciplines, reflecting key principles discussed in recent European policy frameworks, such as transparency, standardization, and reusability [5]. As such, `dataquieR` contributes to the development of cross-domain research data infrastructures and data quality practices beyond its original field.

Keywords: data quality, metadata, open source software, R package, reproducibility, standardization

Resources

- dataquieR v.2.5.1. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.dataquieR>. Open source software that enables to conduct automated data quality assessments using R.
- Metadata setup for dataquieR. https://dataquality.qihs.uni-greifswald.de/VIN_Annotation_of_Metadata.html. Documentation of the metadata structure and attributes.
- TEHDAS Joint Action (2022). <https://tehdas.eu/tehdas1/results/tehdas-proposals-for-data-quality-and-utility-in-ehds/>. Framework supporting structured and reusable quality metadata in health data infrastructures.

Author contributions

EK – Software, Writing, original draft, Writing – review & editing, ES – Software, Writing, review & editing, StS – Software, Writing, review & editing, COS – Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Software, Writing, review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

We gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – project number 442326535, and SCHM 2744/3-4. The development of dataquieR was further supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 825903 (euCanShare project). The financial support by the German National Cohort (NAKO) as funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF: 01ER1301A and 01ER1801A) is also gratefully acknowledged.

Acknowledgement

This work was done as part of the NFDI4Health Consortium and is published on behalf of this Consortium (www.nfdi4health.de).

References

- [1] L. Ehrlinger and W. Wöß, "A Survey of Data Quality Measurement and Monitoring Tools," *Front. Big Data*, vol. 5, Mar. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2022.850611>
- [2] C. O. Schmidt et al., "Facilitating harmonized data quality assessments. A data quality framework for observational health research data collections with software implementations in R," *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 63, Apr. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01252-7>
- [3] J. Mariño, E. Kasbohm, S. Struckmann, L. A. Kapsner, and C. O. Schmidt, "R Packages for Data Quality Assessments and Data Monitoring: A Software Scoping Review with Recommendations for Future Developments," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 9, Art. no. 9, Jan. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12094238>

- [4] S. Struckmann, J. Mariño, E. Kasbohm, E. Salogni, and C. O. Schmidt, "dataquieR 2: An updated R package for FAIR data quality assessments in observational studies and electronic health record data," *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 9, no. 98, p. 6581, Jun. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.06581>
- [5] C. Lacagnina et al., "Towards a Data Quality Framework for EOSC," Jan. 2023, Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/7515816>. [Accessed: Apr. 12, 2024]